

THE USE OF ADDRESS TERMS IN POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE MEANINGS IN THE WORKS OF WRITER T. KAYIPBERGENOV

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the stylistic usage of address terms (vocatives) in the literary works of the prominent Karakalpak writer T. Kayipbergenov. The research shows that vocatives serve as a powerful stylistic device with strong emotional-expressive coloring and significant aesthetic value. The author analyzes their application in both positive and negative meanings. Positive vocatives, which prevail in the writer's works, express endearment, respect, friendship, kinship, and intimacy, often using possessive affixes and the emotional element "jan". Negative vocatives, though used less frequently, are skillfully applied to convey dissatisfaction, anger, contempt, and rebuke without losing artistic quality. The findings demonstrate that T. Kayipbergenov employs address terms not only to attract attention but also to create vivid images, reveal character traits, and strengthen the emotional impact of the text. Through a rich combination of everyday, archaic, and historical vocatives, the writer displays his unique individual style and high mastery of the Karakalpak literary language.

Linguists define the main objectives of studying the language of literary works as follows: revealing the foundations and specific characteristics of the language of a literary work, describing the important qualitative features of figurative-expressive language, and identifying the patterns of artistic word creation. In accordance with this, Professor A. Bekbergenov highlighted issues related to revealing and describing the tools and methods of artistic word formation¹.

The style of a literary work, like other styles, is distinguished by its emotional-expressiveness and artistic tools, while adhering to the norms of the literary language, its phonetic and grammatical rules, as well as the orthographic and orthoepic principles of the literary language. In it, one can see the writer's individual skill in word selection and word

¹Balaqaev, M., Janpeisov, E., Tomanov, M., Manasbaev, B. Qazaq tili stilistikası (Stylistics of Kazakh language). Tashkent, 2008.

usage. For example, writer T. Kayipbergenov effectively used folk oral creations in all of his works to achieve figurativeness. He used many words in figurative (metaphorical) meanings.

Literary literature performs communicative and aesthetic functions. Therefore, the scope of usage of the literary artistic style is very wide; it makes maximum use of all stylistic possibilities and may even deviate from the norms of the literary language.

From the point of view of its social function, literary literature is distinguished by its aesthetic impact. Among functional styles, the style that can cover all aspects of life is the style of literary literature. It is characterized by the need for proper creative use in accordance with its figurativeness, emotional general intelligibility, genre characteristics, structure, and aesthetic requirements.

The expressive means of language stylistic colors in words, the expressive features of morphological forms and syntactic constructions do not appear separately in the text, but together create the artistry of the work and present the content figuratively. Therefore, all elements in the language of the work that possess figurativeness must be analyzed together, as a single whole.

When studying the language of a literary work, it is necessary to determine how the writer used the artistic means of language in that particular work, how he utilized words, word forms, and syntactic constructions to create artistic images, as well as his individual skill in word usage and his style. Only then can the writer's linguistic features, individual style, and the specific characteristics of the language of the literary work be revealed.

The stylistic use of address terms (vocatives) in literary works stands out due to its inherent powerful stylistic features. Address terms possess the power to exert an aesthetic influence on a person, and through them, the master of artistic expression depicts the world around us in a figurative and artistic way. When analyzing the language of literary works, we can see the wide usage of vocatives.

"Vocatives are considered a powerful stylistic device, as they indicate the person or object (animate or inanimate) to which the speaker's words are directed². Vocatives express the speaker's attitude toward the listener and carry an evaluative character (positive, negative, neutral, or elevated)."

In the works of writer T. Kayipbergenov, the address terms used are applied in accordance with the meaning of each word and in a stylistically appropriate manner. Any word is taken into account along with its meaning, stylistic features, expressive and emotional coloring, and its usage. The correct use of vocatives for stylistic purposes is also considered appropriate and goal-oriented.

In the style of literary literature, evaluative address terms, while possessing emotional-expressive coloring, not only describe a word but also characterize it and express an attitude toward it. Since these attitudes vary, we found it appropriate to divide them into **positive-meaning** and **negative-meaning** vocatives.

In the Karakalpak language, especially in literary works, words are used in various meanings and in different ways. In every poet's and writer's choice of words, their

² Abdinazimov, Sh. Til – milletniñ ruwxı (Language is the spirit of the nation). Tashkent, 2017.

individuality, personal style, and skill in creating images become visible and distinct³. In the works of writer T. Kayipbergenov's, the overwhelming majority of the address terms used consist of vocatives with positive meaning.

Positive-meaning vocatives most often express emotions of endearment, respect, friendship, harmony, kinship, and closeness. For example:

- Tárbiyashımızǵa oylasıwǵa barıp edim, ol: - Seniń de bir ámengeriń tabılsa táájip emes, *qızım*, biraq ózińniń de esiń endi, detdomǵa kelgendegi lichnoe deloń menen tanısıp, izlew xat jazıp kór, - dedi. (I went to consult with our educator, and she said: - It wouldn't be surprising if you also find a mentor, *my daughter*, but you should come to your senses now. Go to the children's home, familiarize yourself with your personal file, and try writing a request letter)⁴.

- Júda jaqsı, *qaraǵım*, otır, shay isheyik, úyde ekewimizden basqa adam bolmaydı. (Very good, *my dear*, sit down, let's drink some tea. There will be no one else at home except the two of us)⁵.

- *Dospan*, aytshı, bereket tap, búgin bul jaǵadan Mirjiq ótpedi me? - Kóre almadım. - Keshir meni, *Dospan*, bola ma? Nabada, onı korseń, meniń kelgenimdi tuydırma, bola ma? (*Dospan*, tell me, for goodness' sake, didn't Mirjiq pass by this shore today? - I didn't see him. - Forgive me, *Dospan*, okay?)⁶.

- *Erjan aǵa*, raykom sizge, tuwısqan adamǵa jay berip, qate islemegen bolsa kerek, - dedi Najimov sóziniń aqırında. Awa, siz kewli keń adamsız, *Nisan Nájimovich*. (*Erjan aǵa*, it seems the district committee was right to give you, as a relative, a place - they didn't make a mistake, - Najimov said at the end of his speech. - Yes, you are a very generous person, *Nisan Najimovich*)⁷.

In the given examples, the vocatives in the first and second sentences take the possessive affix, which indicates the speaker's close, intimate, or belonging relationship with the person being addressed, thereby conveying a stylistic meaning of affection.

Meanings such as endearment and respect, in addition to possessive affixes, are skillfully expressed by the writer through the emotional word "jan" (soul/dear) placed before or after words denoting closeness, as well as through the endearment affix "-jan". For example:

- *Áy, sheshejanay*, - dedi qatańbas kempir. Ol biysharada ne jazıq bar deyseń? (Oh, *dear mother*, - said the stubborn old woman. What fault does the poor woman have, you think?)⁸

- Qáydem bileyin, *qurdasjan*, sonı bilgende úseytip júremiz be, seniń menen oylasayın degende basqa birew menen qashıp kete bersem be eken deyjaqpan ǵoy! (How should I know, *dear peer*, if we knew that, would we be wandering around like this? When I wanted to consult with you, I thought maybe I should just run away with someone else!)⁹

Writer T. Kayipbergenov used vocatives expressing friendship and harmony with great stylistic skill, efficiency, and conciseness. Such vocatives also convey emotions of endearment, respect, and politeness. For example:

³ Berdimuratov, E. Kórkem ádebiyat stiliń tiykarǵı ózgeshelikleri (Main features of the literary style) // Amiwdaya journal. 1973. № 5.

⁴ Kayipbergenov, T. "Novellas". - Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 2018, "Sleepless Nights", p. 368.

⁵ Kayipbergenov, T. Daughter of Karakalpak (Қарақалпақ қызы). – Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1975, p 9.

⁶ Ibid. p 7.

⁷ Kayipbergenov, T. "Novellas". - Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 2018, "The Apple of the Eye", p. 22.

⁸ Kayipbergenov T. Daughter of Karakalpak (Qaraqalpaq qızı). – Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1975, p 9.

⁹ Ibid., p. 27

- *Perixan*, atıń alısqa alıp qashtı ma! Sıyırlardı quwma, *aynalayın!* Ekewi de buwaz sıyır, erkine jayıla bersin! (*Perixan*, has your horse run far away! Don't chase the cows, *my darling!* Both of them are pregnant, let them graze freely!¹⁰

The address terms in these examples are depicted by the writer in a highly emotional and artistic manner. The writer could have presented these vocatives in a simple and ordinary way, but he portrayed them beautifully and expressively so that they would have a stronger impact on the reader.

In the works of T. Kayipbergenov, one also encounters vocatives formed from words that are rarely used in everyday life and have a limited scope of usage. These are vocatives based on archaisms and historical words. Obsolete words hold great importance in literary depiction as they help convey the color of the era.

Historical vocatives that is, address words related to objects, actions, and concepts that have fallen out of use, or words that have become obsolete due to the emergence of new terms are used in the writer's works to reflect the true picture of the time. For example:

- Kelinshek jawlıgın kóterip: - Usılar, -dedi,-*xalayıq, káramatlı Xiywa xanınıń adamları*, bolğan shınılıqtı aytayın. (The daughter-in-law lifted her headscarf and said: - These people here are the men of the *miraculous Khan of Khiva*. I will tell the whole truth.¹¹

- *Ullı biy*, is shataq, - dedi Áliy entigip hám ishtegiler esitip qoymasın degen oy menen sıbırlanıp seyledi, -xan shabarmanı óldi. (*Great biy*, there is trouble, said Aliy breathlessly and whispered so that those inside would not hear, — the Khan's messenger has been killed)¹²

- Qánekey, *molleke*, bizlerdi ajirastır. Basqa nárese kerek emes. (Come on, *dear mullah*, divorce us. We don't need anything else¹³).

In the works of T. Kayipbergenov, the used address terms are not always uniform; stylistically, they often complement the main vocative, adding expressive emotion and color. For example:

- *Abısınlar, kelinshekler, qızlar-aw*, - dedi Jumagúl olarğa. Men sizlerge bir shınılıqtı aytqım kelip turğoy, qolay kórseñizler? (Dear Sisters-in-laws, *dear daughters-in-laws, girls* - said Jumagul to them. - I want to tell you the truth. Would you like to hear it?)¹⁴

In such constructions, homogeneous members and generalized vocatives are used together. In the writer's works, one can also find vocatives with very strong emotional-expressive meaning.

Thus, the address terms used in the works of writer T. Kayipbergenov are characterized as positive-meaning vocatives that describe the mentioned words.

In the style of literary language, words from all elements of our vocabulary are not used arbitrarily, but in accordance with the demands of the particular work. This especially gives the character's speech its unique features, thereby adding linguistic reality, artistry, and semantic depth to the work. Along with the positive use of address terms in literary works, negative vocatives are also used when describing people and objects. In them, as in positive vocatives, emotional-expressive meaning prevails. They play an important role in creating the

¹⁰ Kayipbergenov T. "Novellas". - Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 2018, "The Secret Known Only to You", p. 108.

¹¹ Kayipbergenov T "The Unfortunates" (Baxitsizlar), Nukus: Karakalpakstan, Bilim, 2019, p. 177

¹² Kayipbergenov T "The Unfortunates" (Baxitsizlar), p. 72

¹³ Kayipbergenov T. Daughter of Karakalpak (Qaraqalpaq qızı). – Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1975, p 6.

¹⁴ Ibid, 221 p.

impact of the depicted event or phenomenon. Depending on the writer's attitude toward the depicted event or subject, such vocatives are used as a tool based on its negative traits. The writer has also skillfully used negative-meaning vocatives with emotional-expressive coloring where appropriate. For example:

- Asqınlama, *ğaz*, tek pãrdiñ sulıwlıǵı ele gózzallıq emes! - dedi oǵan Perdegúl. (Don't overdo it, *goose!* Just because a duck is beautiful doesn't mean it's the only beauty! Perdegul said to her)¹⁵.

- Sarqıt ber, *júwernemek!* – Jaqsı niyetten bos qaldırma! (Give me the leftovers, *you worthless creature!* Don't leave good intentions empty! ¹⁶

- Qanday biyádep iytseñ, *qatın!*-dep bolıp, Turımbetke jın kózlenip jekirindi. (What an impudent *dog you are, woman!* — shouted Turımbet, his eyes blazing with rage)¹⁷.

- *Áy, jaman*, shappattay qatınǵa betiñnen aldırıp qazıqtay qaqayıp ne qılıp tursañ! (Hey, *evil woman*, why are you standing there like a stake after letting that flat-faced woman slap you!)¹⁸

- Sen, *bále*, hayaldı tañlap alǵan ekenseñ. (You, *disaster*, seem to have chosen a wife¹⁹. (Ibid., p. 150)

- *Háy, aq qurash*, jóniñe júr!-dep basına áskeriy soppas kiygen sarı atlı jas jigit oǵan shawıp kelipabay etse de, onǵa burılmaǵanlardı ózi de bir xoshametley qalmadı. (Hey, *white worm*, mind your own business! - shouted a young rider in a military hat as he galloped toward him)²⁰

In these examples, the writer has skillfully depicted negative-meaning vocatives in a very polite, artistic, and not overly rude manner. Through these vocatives, the writer characterizes people's behavior, habits, and demands, expressing his own thoughts and feelings. Additionally, the writer effectively used vocatives that convey hatred, cursing, and revenge. For example:

- Qısqartsaña, *ladan!* Anıǵın bilmey nege háwlireseñ? (Cut it short, *idiot!* Why are you making a fuss without knowing the truth? ²¹

- *Há, náletiy urılar?!-* dep qısıq iyinlisi uratuǵınday dónip, qamshısın kóterip kelip qaldı. (Hey, *cursed thieves?! -* he turned sharply as if about to strike...) ²²

In these examples, the writer artistically and figuratively expressed emotions of hatred, cursing, and revenge through vocatives. These vocatives reach the person in an artistic form and produce a negative effect.

Therefore, the address terms in the works of T. Kayipbergenov are not used merely to attract the listener's attention, but, possessing emotional-expressive coloring, they are used in both positive and negative meanings. They describe words, express attitudes toward them, and portray them artistically, effectively, and skillfully. This is a distinctive feature of the writer's individual style.

¹⁵ Kayipbergenov, T. "Novellas". - Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 2018, "Sleepless Nights", p. 389.

¹⁶ Kayipbergenov T. Daughter of Karakalpak (Qaraqalpaq qızı). – Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1975, p 74.

¹⁷ Ibid., p. 74

¹⁸ Ibid., p. 150

¹⁹ Kayipbergenov T. Daughter of Karakalpak (Qaraqalpaq qızı). – Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1975, p 150.

²⁰ Ibid., p. 284

²¹ Ibid., p. 248

²² Ibid., p. 248

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